

LIFE PREDICTION OF COMPOSITE BEAM COLUMNS UNDER GENERAL LOADING CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a consistent creep buckling analysis of viscoelastic laminated columns under general loading conditions. The problem is formulated in terms of convolution integral operators and is solved by means of the quasi-elastic method. As a result of the analysis, the creep buckling response of composite beam columns is examined and compared with that of identical homogeneous structures. The study leads to general conclusions regarding the long-term performance of composite beam columns and the assessment of their useful life.

Keywords: laminated beam columns, composites, creep, viscoelasticity, buckling

I. INTRODUCTION

At present, research activities in many technological fields are directed towards developing new generations of advanced composite materials. Attention is particularly focused on laminated composites due to their demonstrated ability to satisfy the requirements of high strength and toughness combined with low weight.

Typically, laminated composite materials are fabricated from unidirectional layers of polymeric matrix reinforced by graphite, glass, silicon carbide or aramid fibers. The layers are combined in a certain stacking sequence, pressed together and hardened into a solid layered structure. The number, orientation, sequence and composition of the layers determine the global properties of the laminate. Respectively, by changing the lamination variables, one can create composite materials with new improved characteristics.

However, the analysis of composite laminates often presents unprecedented problems due to the fact that their behavior is more complex and less predictable than that of traditional isotropic materials. Of particular concern is the compression response of thin-walled composite structures since they tend to exhibit various forms of instability under critical conditions. Considerable research efforts in this subject area have been mainly directed towards the buckling analysis of elastic composite plates, see Refs. [1,2]. More recent studies, e.g. Refs. [3-5], deal with various creep buckling problems of viscoelastic composite structures.

This paper is a continuation of the work presented in Ref. [5] concerning the response of

viscoelastic composite columns in compression. The study deals with the creep buckling problem of laminated beam columns subjected to a combined action of compression and bending. The objective of the analysis is to examine the general creep buckling problem of composite beam columns with time-dependent properties and provide an assessment of their useful life.

II. GENERAL PROBLEM

Consider a laminated beam column composed of n layers of different materials bonded together. The structure has a rectangular cross-section ($b \times h$), where h denotes the total thickness of the laminate

$$h = \sum_{k=1}^n h_k \quad (1)$$

in which h_k ($k = 1, 2, \dots, n$) represents the thickness of an individual layer.

The beam column is hinge supported and may have an initial shape imperfection defined by the function $w_i(x)$ where x denotes the axial coordinate. The structure is subjected to a combined action of an axial compressive force P , distributed lateral pressure $q(x)$, and bending moment M_0 . The loads are applied instantaneously at the time $t = 0$ and sustained at $t > 0$.

The material properties of an individual layer are defined by the constitutive equations of the linear viscoelastic theory in the form

$$\sigma_k = E_k^* [\epsilon_k], \quad (k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (2)$$

where

$$E_k^* = E_k (1 - R_k^*) = \frac{E_k}{1 + C_k^*}, \quad (k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (3)$$

in which E_k denote the elastic moduli; and R_k^* and C_k^* are symbolic notations used to identify the relaxation and creep operators, respectively. In particular,

$$C_k^* [\sigma_k] = \int_0^t C_k(t-\tau) \sigma_k(\tau) d\tau, \quad (k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (4)$$

where the kernels C_k characterize the creep properties of the layers.

In Equation 2, ϵ_k denotes the axial strain of the k -th layer. Due to the deformation compatibility between the layers

$$\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2 = \dots = \epsilon_n = \epsilon \quad (5)$$

According to the Bernoulli-Euler theory, ϵ is defined in the form

$$\epsilon = - \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + z \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \quad (6)$$

where u and w denote, respectively, the axial and lateral displacement components of the beam column. Note that the displacements u and w are functions of the coordinate x and time t .

Based on the above assumptions, the creep buckling response of the composite beam column is defined by a set of two simultaneous equations

$$\begin{pmatrix} Q_1^* & Q_2^* \\ Q_2^* & Q_3^* \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_0 \\ \kappa \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} P \\ M \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where the axial strain $\epsilon_0 = -\partial u/\partial x$, the curvature $\kappa = -\partial^2 w/\partial x^2$, and Q_k^* ($k = 1, 2, 3$) are integral operators defined by

$$Q_1^* = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k E_k^* \quad (8)$$

$$Q_2^* = \sum_{k=1}^n \beta_k E_k^* \quad (9)$$

$$Q_3^* = \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k E_k^* \quad (10)$$

in which

$$\alpha_k = \int_{A_k} dA, \quad \beta_k = \int_{A_k} z dA, \quad \gamma_k = \int_{A_k} z^2 dA, \quad (k=1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (11)$$

Equation 7 can be reduced to a single integrodifferential equation

$$[Q_1^* Q_3^* - (Q_2^*)^2] \left[\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right] = Q_2^* [P] - Q_1^* [M] \quad (12)$$

the solution of which must satisfy the following boundary and initial conditions

$$w(0, t) = w(l, t) = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$w(x, 0) = w_\theta(x) \quad (14)$$

where $w_\theta(x)$ denotes the lateral deflection of the beam column at the time of the load application.

In Equation 12, the bending moment M is defined by

$$M = Pw_i + \frac{1}{2} Q_o x (1-x) + M_o + Pw \quad (15)$$

The function of integral operators $Q_1^* Q_3^* - (Q_2^*)^2$ can be determined following the algebra rules for linear integral operators of Stieltjes convolution type, see e.g. Ref. [6]. The kernels of these operators are determined from creep experiments as discussed in Refs. [6-8].

Note that, in the case of symmetrically laminated as well as homogeneous beam columns, the operator $Q_2^* = 0$. Respectively, Equation 12 assumes the form

$$Q_3^* \left[\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right] = -M \quad (16)$$

The creep buckling problem defined by Equation 12 can be solved by means of the quasi-elastic method suggested in Ref. [9] for linear viscoelastic stress analysis. The method is based on the fact that the response of many viscoelastic materials with fading memory can be approximated by the behavior of a fictitious elastic material with time-dependent properties. The accuracy of quasi-elastic solutions is shown to be sufficient for engineering applications in the cases when the creep

behavior of viscoelastic materials is characterized by low deformation rates, Refs. [9, 10].

The quasi-elastic method implies that the integral operators E_k^* are replaced by

$$E_k'(t) = E_k / [1 + \Psi_k(t)]; \quad (k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (17)$$

where $\Psi_k(t)$ denote the creep functions

$$\Psi_k(t) = \int_0^t C_k(t-\tau) d\tau, \quad (k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (18)$$

which characterize the creep properties of the individual layers of the laminate.

As a result of this approach, the integrodifferential Equation 12 is replaced by an ordinary differential equation in which time, t , is a parameter. By assigning various values of this parameter one arrives at a series of elastic buckling problems the solution of which provides the quasi-elastic approximation w' of the lateral deflection w . The quasi-elastic solution of the creep buckling problem of homogeneous beam columns is given in Ref. [11].

III. RESPONSE OF SYMMETRIC LAMINATES

Consider the long-term response of symmetrically laminated beam columns. Introducing Equations 10 and 15 into Equation 16, and using the quasi-elastic method one arrives at

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\gamma_k E_k}{1 + \Psi_k(t)} \right) \frac{d^2 w'}{dx^2} + P w' = - (P w_i + \frac{1}{2} q_0 x(1-x) + M_0) \quad (19)$$

where w' denotes the quasi-elastic approximation of the lateral deflection w . At the time $t = 0$, the function w' coincides with the exact solution w_0 . Respectively, w' satisfies the initial condition in the form of Equation 14.

In Equation 19, the function

$$S(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\gamma_k E_k}{1 + \Psi_k(t)} \quad (20)$$

can be treated as a time-dependent effective stiffness of the laminated beam column. In the case of homogeneous structures, Equation 20 reduces to

$$S_h(t) = \frac{IE}{1 + \Psi(t)} \quad (21)$$

where I denotes the inertia moment of the cross-sectional area of the beam column. Note that the creep function $\Psi(t)$ defines the long-term material response. A creep function that tends to a certain constant as $t \rightarrow \infty$, i.e.

$$\Psi(\infty) = \Psi_\infty = \text{const} \quad (22)$$

represents viscoelastic materials with limited creep properties. For materials with unlimited creep, $\Psi(\infty) = \infty$.

In order to examine in detail the creep buckling response of a laminated beam column consider, for example, a combined action of axial compression and uniform lateral pressure. Assume that $w_i = 0$ and $M_0 = 0$.

Based on the solution of the respective elastic buckling problem for homogeneous beam columns, see Ref. [12], the amplitude of w' is obtained in the form

$$A(t) = \frac{q l^2}{8P} \left[\frac{8S(t)}{Pl^2} \left(\frac{1}{\cos \sqrt{\frac{Pl^2}{4S(t)}}} - 1 \right) - 1 \right] \quad (23)$$

where l denotes the length of the beam column.

The creep buckling characteristic of the beam column in the normalized form

$$\frac{A(t)}{A(0)} = \frac{8 D(t) \left[\frac{1}{\cos \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\lambda/D(t)} \right)} - 1 \right] - \lambda \pi^2}{8 \left[\frac{1}{\cos \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\lambda} \right)} - 1 \right] - \lambda \pi^2} \quad (24)$$

where $D(t) = S(t)/S(0)$, $\lambda = P/P_e$, and P_e denotes the critical load of the respective elastic laminated beam column

$$P_e = \left(\frac{\pi}{l} \right)^2 S(0) \quad (25)$$

Equation 24 indicates that the function $A(t)$ is limited in time if $D(t)$ tends to a constant value D_∞ as $t \rightarrow \infty$, and if $\lambda/D_\infty < 1$. The magnitude of λ defined as

$$\lambda_s = D_\infty \quad (26)$$

represents a safe load limit below which the creep buckling deformation of the composite beam column tends to stabilize in time. Alternatively, if $\lambda > \lambda_s$, the function $A(t)$ becomes unlimited. The latter case, however, cannot be treated within the scope of this study since the concept of infinite deformations is inconsistent with the basic assumptions of the linear deformation theory adopted in the analysis.

According to Equation 24, the creep buckling response of composite beam columns depends on the number, sequence, and material properties of the individual layers of the laminate. This result is illustrated by a numerical example using a beam column composed of eight layers of equal thickness, $h_k = h/8$, ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 8$). Creep buckling characteristics are computed for two compositions of the layers defined as SC1 and SC2. Specifically, SC1 refers to the case when the layers 1, 3, 6, and 8 have viscoelastic material properties characterized by an instantaneous elastic modulus E and a creep function $\Psi(t)$. The layers 2, 4, 5, and 7 are considered to be elastic with the same elastic modulus E . In the case SC2, the sequence of the layers is reversed, i.e. the layers 1, 3, 6, and 8 are elastic, whereas the layers 2, 4, 5, and 7 are viscoelastic with the same material characteristics as the layers 1, 3, 6, and 8 in the case SC1. The responses of both structures are compared with that of a homogeneous viscoelastic beam column which is subjected to the same loading conditions and has the same material properties as the viscoelastic layers of the beam columns SC1 and SC2. In all cases, the creep function $\Psi(t)$ is defined as

$$\Psi(t) = 0.5 [1 - \exp(-\mu t)] \quad (27)$$

representing a limited creep viscoelastic material, $\Psi(\infty) = 0.5$. In Equation 27, μt denotes nondimensional time.

Using Equations 11, 20 and 26, for all beam columns under consideration, the respective safe load limits are obtained such as

$$(\lambda_g)_{SC1} = 0.771; (\lambda_g)_{SC2} = 0.896; (\lambda_g)_h = 0.667 \quad (28)$$

The creep buckling characteristics are computed for five different values of λ as shown in Figure 1.

The obtained results indicate that, for $\lambda < \lambda_g$, i.e. $\lambda = 0.3$ and $\lambda = 0.5$, time-dependent deformations tend to stabilize, whereas at λ approaching the safe load limit, they increase at accelerating rates. In general, the response of the homogeneous beam column is characterized by much higher creep rates in relation to its composite counterparts. From the diagram, one can also observe visible differences between the behavior of the structures in the cases SC1 and SC2. This indicates that the long-term response of composite laminates depends on the sequence and composition of their constituent layers.

Figure 1. Creep buckling characteristics

IV. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The paper presents the creep buckling analysis of viscoelastic laminated beam columns subjected simultaneously to bending and compression. The problem is formulated in terms of convolution integral operators and is solved by means of the the quasi-elastic method.

The results of the analysis indicate that the creep buckling response of composite beam columns depends on a number of parameters including the number, sequence and material properties of the layers of the laminate. For materials with limited creep characteristics, one can determine a safe load limit below which the time-dependent deformations of the structures tend to stabilize in time. As the magnitude of the axial compressive force approaches the safe load limit, the behavior of beam columns is characterized by accelerated deformation rates. This type of response can generate irreversible changes in the material leading to failure. Respectively, the time at which deformation rates become significant can be treated as a terminal point with respect to the useful life of composite beam columns subjected to creep buckling.

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